

A/chicken/Republic of Macedonia/AR1167-102131/2017	261634	HSN8	Anne Pohlmann (Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut)	Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut	University "Ss. Cyril and Methodius" , Veterinary institute, Department of Avian diseases
A/common teal/Korea/W547/2016	266417	HSN8			
A/common teal/Korea/W549/2016	266418	HSN8			
A/common teal/Korea/W548/2016	266419	HSN8			
A/common teal/Korea/W550/2016	266420	HSN8			
A/common teal/Korea/W555/2017	266421	HSN8			
A/chicken/Belgium/807/2017	266536	HSN8			
A/peacock/Belgium/1017/2017	266537	HSN8			
A/Cygnus olor/Belgium/1567/2017	266538	HSN8			
A/green-winged teal/Egypt/871/2016	267135	HSN8			
A/green-winged teal/Egypt/877/2016	267136	HSN8			
A/duck/Egypt/5519/2017	268021	HSN8	Abdel-Satar Mohamed Arafa (Animal Health Research Institute)	Animal Health Research Institute	National Laboratory for Veterinary Quality Control on Poultry production- Animal Health Research Institute
A/duck/Egypt/F446/2017	268513	HSN8	Abdel-Satar Mohamed Arafa (Animal Health Research Institute)	Animal Health Research Institute	National Laboratory for Veterinary Quality Control on Poultry production- Animal Health Research Institute
A/Bk_swan/NL-Den Oever/16013973-002/2016	268618	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Bl_h_gull/NL-Slootdorp/16014102-002/2016	268619	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Buzzard/NL-Durgedam/16015100-004/2016	268620	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/C_Gull/NL-Slootdorp/16014102-003/2016	268621	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Ch/NL-Abbega/X16015736/2016	268622	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Ch/NL-Boven Leeuwen/16016151-006-010/2016	268623	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Ch/NL-Den Oever/16014231-001/2016	268624	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Ch/NL-Hiure/16016112-001-005/2016	268625	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Ch/NL-Rhenen/16016141_006/2016	268626	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Ch/NL-Zoeterwoude/16016484_021-025/2016	268627	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Crow/NL-Oostwoud/16015372-004/2016	268628	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Dk/NL-Biddinghuizen/16014829-011-015/2016	268629	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Dk/NL-Biddinghuizen/16015083-016-020/2016	268630	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Dk/NL-Biddinghuizen/16015145-021-025/2016	268631	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Dk/NL-Kamperveen/16016104-001-005/2016	268632	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Dk/NL-Rotterdam/16014008-001-005/2016	268633	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Dk/NL-Stolwijk/16016291-016-020/2016	268634	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-Akkur/16015817-003/2016	268635	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-De Waal (Texel)/16014891-003/2016	268636	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-De Waal (Texel)/16014891-004/2016	268637	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-Drieborg (Dollard)/16015513-001/2016	268638	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-Ennematl-Groningen/16015704-001/2016	268639	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-Ferwert/16015273-002/2016	268640	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-Gouda/16015824-001/2016	268641	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-Greonterp/16015653-001/2016	268642	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-Groningen/16015376-003/2016	268643	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-Leeuwarden/16015699-002/2016	268644	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-Leidschendam/16015697-007/2016	268645	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-Reeuwijk/16015903-003/2016	268646	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-Terschelling/16015692-010/2016	268647	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-Vianen/16015917-006/2016	268648	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-Walterswald/16015923-003/2016	268649	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-West Graftdijk/16015746-003/2016	268650	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-Warmer/16016143-002/2016	268651	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-Zoeterwoude/16015702-010/2016	268652	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eur_Wig/NL-Zwolle/16015820-002/2016	268653	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/G_c_grebe/NL-Monnickendam/16013865-009-010/2016	268654	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Go/NL-Roggebotsluis/16014462-010/2016	268655	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Gr_bd_bk_gull/NL-Slootdorp/16014102-005/2016	268656	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Grey_Go/NL-Groot Ammers/16015901-012/2016	268657	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Gull/NL-Marker Wadden/16014466-020/2016	268658	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Gull1/NL-Marker Wadden/16014466-011/2016	268659	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Gull10/NL-Marker Wadden/16014466-014/2016	268660	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/L-bl-ba-gull/NL-Sovon/16014324-014/2016	268661	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/M_Swan/NL-Roggebotsluis/16014462-019/2016	268662	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Magpie/NL-Voerendam/16014331-002/2016	268663	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Mal/NL-Isselmeulen/16015448-002/2016	268664	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Mal/NL-Maxtenbroek/16015378-002/2016	268665	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/P_falcon/NL-Vrouwenpolder (Zeeland)/16015510-001/2016	268666	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Sea_eagle/NL-Assen/16015398-002/2016	268667	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/T_Dk/NL-Almeerder Zand/16014341-003/2016	268668	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/T_Dk/NL-Monnickendam/16013865-006-008/2016	268669	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/T_Dk/NL-Roggebotsluis/16014462-015/2016	268670	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/T_Dk/NL-Rotterdam/16014155-001/2016	268671	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/T_Dk/NL-Werkendam/16014159-002/2016	268672	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/T_Dk/NL-Werkendam/16014159-003/2016	268673	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/T_Dk/NL-Zeeuwolde/16013976-001/2016	268674	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/T_Dk/NL-Zeeuwolde/16013976-001-003/2016	268675	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/T_Dk/NL-Zeeuwolde/16013976-004/2016	268676	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/T_Dk/NL-Zeeuwolde/16013976-004-006/2016	268677	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/T_Dk/NL-Zeeuwolde/16013976-005/2016	268678	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/T_Dk/NL-Zeeuwolde/16013976-006/2016	268679	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/T_Dk/NL-Zuidoost Beemster/16014148-002/2016	268680	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/T_Dk/NL-Zuidoost Beemster/16014148-009/2016	268681	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Teal/NL-Ferwert/16015273-013/2016	268682	HSN8	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Goose/Czech Republic/136-17_1/2017 (HSN8)	268930	HSN8	Alexander Nagy (State Veterinary Institute Prague)	State Veterinary Institute Prague	State Veterinary Institute Prague
A/mute swan/Czech Republic/1058-17/2017 (HSN8)	268940	HSN8	Alexander Nagy (State Veterinary Institute Prague)	State Veterinary Institute Prague	State Veterinary Institute Prague
A/mute swan/Czech Republic/1060-17/2017 (HSN8)	268941	HSN8	Alexander Nagy (State Veterinary Institute Prague)	State Veterinary Institute Prague	State Veterinary Institute Prague
A/mallard/Czech Republic/1219-17_1/2017 (HSN8)	268947	HSN8	Alexander Nagy (State Veterinary Institute Prague)	State Veterinary Institute Prague	State Veterinary Institute Prague
A/Goose/Hungary/17261/2017	271704	HSN8	Adam Dan (Danam.Vet.Molbio)	Danam.Vet.Molbio	National Food Chain Safety Office Veterinary Diagnostic Directorate Laboratory for Molecular Biology
A/Goose/Hungary/15729/2017	271705	HSN8	Adam Dan (Danam.Vet.Molbio)	Danam.Vet.Molbio	National Food Chain Safety Office Veterinary Diagnostic Directorate Laboratory for Molecular Biology
A/Goose/Hungary/17051/2017	271706	HSN8	Adam Dan (Danam.Vet.Molbio)	Danam.Vet.Molbio	National Food Chain Safety Office Veterinary Diagnostic Directorate Laboratory for Molecular Biology

A/Goose/Hungary/17580/2017	271707	HSN8	Adam Dan (Danam.Vet.Molbio)	Danam.Vet.Molbio	National Food Chain Safety Office Veterinary Diagnostic Directorate Laboratory for Molecular Biology
A/Goose/Hungary/17985/2017	271708	HSN8	Adam Dan (Danam.Vet.Molbio)	Danam.Vet.Molbio	National Food Chain Safety Office Veterinary Diagnostic Directorate Laboratory for Molecular Biology
A/Goose/Hungary/59763/2016	271709	HSN8	Adam Dan (Danam.Vet.Molbio)	Danam.Vet.Molbio	National Food Chain Safety Office Veterinary Diagnostic Directorate Laboratory for Molecular Biology
A/Mular_d_duck/Hungary/60369/2016	271710	HSN8	Adam Dan (Danam.Vet.Molbio)	Danam.Vet.Molbio	National Food Chain Safety Office Veterinary Diagnostic Directorate Laboratory for Molecular Biology
A/Mular_d_duck/Hungary/62902/2016	271711	HSN8	Adam Dan (Danam.Vet.Molbio)	Danam.Vet.Molbio	National Food Chain Safety Office Veterinary Diagnostic Directorate Laboratory for Molecular Biology
A/Goose/Hungary/63743/2016	271712	HSN8	Adam Dan (Danam.Vet.Molbio)	Danam.Vet.Molbio	National Food Chain Safety Office Veterinary Diagnostic Directorate Laboratory for Molecular Biology
A/Goose/Hungary/64909/2016	271713	HSN8	Adam Dan (Danam.Vet.Molbio)	Danam.Vet.Molbio	National Food Chain Safety Office Veterinary Diagnostic Directorate Laboratory for Molecular Biology
A/Mular_d_duck/Hungary/59163/2016	271714	HSN8	Adam Dan (Danam.Vet.Molbio)	Danam.Vet.Molbio	National Food Chain Safety Office Veterinary Diagnostic Directorate Laboratory for Molecular Biology
A/grey heron/W779/2017	272859	HSN8			
A/chicken/Italy/17VR3078/2017	273846	HSN8	Bianca Zecchin (Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale Delle Venezia)	Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale Delle Venezia	Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale Delle Venezia
A/turkey/Italy/17VIR5878-3/2017	273847	HSN8	Bianca Zecchin (Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale Delle Venezia)	Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale Delle Venezia	Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale Delle Venezia
A/mute swan/Kaliningrad/132/2017	274858	HSN8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Shdhyolkovo/47/2017	275283	HSN8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Rostov-on-Don/44/2017	275287	HSN8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Tatarstan/88/2017	275288	HSN8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/mute_swan/Switzerland/V0244.2-L02307/2017	280674	HSN8	Anne Pohlmann (Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut)	Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut	Institut für Virologie und Immunologie - Bundesamt für Lebensmittelsicherheit und Veterinärwesen
A/turkey/Czech Republic/38-17_1/2017 (HSN8)	282133	HSN8	Alexander Nagy (State Veterinary Institute Prague)	State Veterinary Institute Prague	State Veterinary Institute Prague
A/swan/Italy/17VIR7064-1/2017	282141	HSN8	Bianca Zecchin (Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale Delle Venezia)	Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale Delle Venezia	Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale Delle Venezia
A/goose/Italy/17VIR6358-3/2017	282143	HSN8	Bianca Zecchin (Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale Delle Venezia)	Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale Delle Venezia	Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale Delle Venezia
A/chicken/Czech Republic/988-17/2017 (HSN8)	283129	HSN8	Alexander Nagy (State Veterinary Institute Prague)	State Veterinary Institute Prague	State Veterinary Institute Prague
A/chicken/South_Africa/S2017/08_0336_P3/2017	284004	HSN8	Florette Kathleen Treurnicht (National Institute for Communicable Diseases / Center for Respirat	National Institute for Communicable Diseases	Western Cape Provincial Veterinary Laboratory
A/Geese/South_Africa/S2017/09_0065_P1/2017	285601	HSN8	Florette Kathleen Treurnicht (National Institute for Communicable Diseases / Center for Respirat	National Institute for Communicable Diseases	Western Cape Provincial Veterinary Laboratory
A/Geese/South_Africa/S2017/09_0065_P2/2017	285602	HSN8	Florette Kathleen Treurnicht (National Institute for Communicable Diseases / Center for Respirat	National Institute for Communicable Diseases	Western Cape Provincial Veterinary Laboratory
A/Ostrich/South_Africa/S2017/08_0046_P3/2017	285604	HSN8	Florette Kathleen Treurnicht (National Institute for Communicable Diseases / Center for Respirat	National Institute for Communicable Diseases	Western Cape Provincial Veterinary Laboratory
A/Duck/South_Africa/S2017/08_0340_P1/2017	285606	HSN8	Florette Kathleen Treurnicht (National Institute for Communicable Diseases / Center for Respirat	National Institute for Communicable Diseases	Western Cape Provincial Veterinary Laboratory
A/Chicken/South_Africa/S2017/09_0050_56/2017	285624	HSN8	Florette Kathleen Treurnicht (National Institute for Communicable Diseases / Center for Respirat	National Institute for Communicable Diseases	Western Cape Provincial Veterinary Laboratory
A/Geese/South_Africa/S2017/09_0055_P1/2017	285648	HSN8	Florette Kathleen Treurnicht (National Institute for Communicable Diseases / Center for Respirat	National Institute for Communicable Diseases	Western Cape Provincial Veterinary Laboratory
A/Chicken/South_Africa/S2017/09_0184_63/2017	285649	HSN8	Florette Kathleen Treurnicht (National Institute for Communicable Diseases / Center for Respirat	National Institute for Communicable Diseases	Western Cape Provincial Veterinary Laboratory
A/Ostrich/South_Africa/S2017/08_0046_Af/2017	285650	HSN8	Florette Kathleen Treurnicht (National Institute for Communicable Diseases / Center for Respirat	National Institute for Communicable Diseases	Western Cape Provincial Veterinary Laboratory
A/Guineafoaf/South_Africa/S2017/08_0190_9/2017	285651	HSN8	Florette Kathleen Treurnicht (National Institute for Communicable Diseases / Center for Respirat	National Institute for Communicable Diseases	Western Cape Provincial Veterinary Laboratory
A/Guineafoaf/South_Africa/S2017/08_0243_P2/2017	285652	HSN8	Florette Kathleen Treurnicht (National Institute for Communicable Diseases / Center for Respirat	National Institute for Communicable Diseases	Western Cape Provincial Veterinary Laboratory
A/Geese/South_Africa/S2017/08_0558_P1/2017	285655	HSN8	Florette Kathleen Treurnicht (National Institute for Communicable Diseases / Center for Respirat	National Institute for Communicable Diseases	Western Cape Provincial Veterinary Laboratory
A/Chicken/South_Africa/S2017/08_0561_P1/2017	285658	HSN8	Florette Kathleen Treurnicht (National Institute for Communicable Diseases / Center for Respirat	National Institute for Communicable Diseases	Western Cape Provincial Veterinary Laboratory
A/T_Dk/NL-Werkendam/16014159-001/2016	287564	HSN5	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/M_Swan/NL-Groningen/16015826-001/2016	287565	HSN5	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/spoonbill/Taiwan/DB645/2017	287800	HSN6	Yu-Pin Liu (Animal Health Research Institute)	Animal Health Research Institute	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Duck/Netherlands/17017236-001-005/2017	287906	HSN6	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Duck/Netherlands/17017237-001-005/2017	287907	HSN6	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/chicken/Greece/39_2017/2017	288362	HSN6	James Seekings (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) / Virology Department)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	Thessalonica Veterinary Centre (TVC)
A/chicken/Greece/39_2017b/2017	288363	HSN6	James Seekings (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) / Virology Department)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	Thessalonica Veterinary Centre (TVC)
A/chicken/Greece/39_2017c/2017	288364	HSN6	James Seekings (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) / Virology Department)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	Thessalonica Veterinary Centre (TVC)
A/Mute Swan/Netherlands/17017367-012/2017	288409	HSN6	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Mute Swan/Netherlands/17017377-001/2017	288410	HSN6	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Tufted Duck/Netherlands/17017367-007/2017	288412	HSN6	Saskia Bergervoet (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/mallard/Korea/Jeju-H24/2017	288436	HSN6	Eun-Kyoung Lee (Animal and Plant Quarantine Agency (S-2026))	Animal and Plant Quarantine Agency (S-2145)	Animal and Plant Quarantine Agency (O-2144)
A/duck/Korea/HD1/2017	288437	HSN6	Eun-Kyoung Lee (Animal and Plant Quarantine Agency (S-2026))	Animal and Plant Quarantine Agency (S-2145)	Animal and Plant Quarantine Agency (O-2144)
A/chicken/Korea/Gunsan/2017	288438	HSN8	Eun-Kyoung Lee (Animal and Plant Quarantine Agency (S-2026))	Animal and Plant Quarantine Agency (S-2145)	Animal and Plant Quarantine Agency (O-2144)
A/mute swan/Shimane/3211A001/2017	289173	HSN6			
A/Great Black-backed Gull/Netherlands/1/2017	289713	HSN6	Maria Johanna Poen (Erasmus Medical Center / Department of Virology)	Erasmus Medical Center	Erasmus Medical Center
A/Black-headed Gull/Netherlands/29/2017	289714	HSN6	Maria Johanna Poen (Erasmus Medical Center / Department of Virology)	Erasmus Medical Center	Erasmus Medical Center
A/mute_swan/Switzerland/V361-L0242/2017	291110	HSN6	Anne Pohlmann (Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut)	Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut	Institut für Virologie und Immunologie - Bundesamt für Lebensmittelsicherheit und Veterinärwesen
A/mute_swan/England/AVP_18_001986/2017	292223	HSN6	James Seekings (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) / Virology Department)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)
A/pochard_duck/England/AVP_18_00254/2018	292224	HSN6	James Seekings (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) / Virology Department)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)
A/canada_goose/England/AVS8_180PpoolEP1/2018	292225	HSN6	James Seekings (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) / Virology Department)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)
A/chicken/Kostroma/1718/2017	295027	HSN2	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Rostov-on-Don/1321/2017	297234	HSN8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Rostov-on-Don/1598/2017	297235	HSN8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Republic of Macedonia/466/2017	297388	HSN8	Aleksandar Dodovski (Faculty of Veterinary Medicine Skopje / Department for Avian Diseases)	Croatian Veterinary Institute	Faculty of Veterinary Medicine Skopje
A/chicken/Kostroma/1717/2017	297463	HSN2	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Kostroma/1718/2017	297464	HSN2	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Kostroma/1720/2017	297465	HSN2	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Kostroma/1721/2017	297466	HSN2	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/White-fronted Goose/AN/1-15-12/2016	300547	HSN8	Susanne Koethe (Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut)	Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut	NSC Institute of Experimental and Clinical Veterinary Medicine
A/Ruddy Shelduck/AN/2-14-12/2016	300548	HSN8	Susanne Koethe (Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut)	Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut	NSC Institute of Experimental and Clinical Veterinary Medicine
A/Environmental (EM) /AN/2/17	300562	HSN8	Susanne Koethe (Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut)	Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut	NSC Institute of Experimental and Clinical Veterinary Medicine
A/turkey/Poland/63/2016	300686	HSN8	Edyta Świątęń (National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB)	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB
A/chicken/Poland/34/2017	300687	HSN8	Edyta Świątęń (National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB)	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB
A/domestic_duck/Poland/47/2017	300693	HSN8	Edyta Świątęń (National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB)	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB
A/turkey/Poland/54/2017	300698	HSN8	Edyta Świątęń (National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB)	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB
A/domestic_goose/Poland/69/2017	300699	HSN8	Edyta Świątęń (National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB)	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB
A/turkey/Poland/72/2017	300700	HSN8	Edyta Świątęń (National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB)	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB
A/turkey/Poland/94/2017	300701	HSN8	Edyta Świątęń (National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB)	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB
A/chicken/Poland/101/2017	300702	HSN8	Edyta Świątęń (National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB)	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB
A/domestic_goose/Poland/124/2017	300703	HSN8	Edyta Świątęń (National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB)	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB
A/turkey/Poland/192/2017	300704	HSN8	Edyta Świątęń (National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB)	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB
A/chicken/Poland/263/2017	300712	HSN8	Edyta Świątęń (National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB)	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB
A/mallard/Poland/17/2017	300743	HSN8	Edyta Świątęń (National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB)	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB
A/swan/Poland/32/2017	300744	HSN8	Edyta Świątęń (National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB)	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB
A/wild duck/Poland/57/2017	300745	HSN8	Edyta Świątęń (National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB)	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB
A/swan/Poland/81/2017	300746	HSN5	Edyta Świątęń (National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB)	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB
A/mute_swan/Poland/137/2017	300747	HSN8	Edyta Świątęń (National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB)	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB	National Veterinary Research Institut Poland, PIWet-PIB
A/Mandarin_duck/Korea/K17-1887/2017	303637	HSN6	Jung Hoon Kwon (Konkuk University / College of Veterinary Medicine)	Konkuk University	Avian diseases laboratory, College of Veterinary Medicine, Konkuk University
A/Mandarin_duck/Korea/K17-1889/2017	303638	HSN6	Jung Hoon Kwon (Konkuk University / College of Veterinary Medicine)	Konkuk University	Avian diseases laboratory, College of Veterinary Medicine, Konkuk University
A/Mandarin_duck/Korea/K17-1891/2017	303639	HSN6	Jung Hoon Kwon (Konkuk University / College of Veterinary Medicine)	Konkuk University	Avian diseases laboratory, College of Veterinary Medicine, Konkuk University
A/Mandarin_duck/Korea/K17-1893/2017	303640	HSN6	Jung Hoon Kwon (Konkuk University / College of Veterinary Medicine)	Konkuk University	Avian diseases laboratory, College of Veterinary Medicine, Konkuk University

A/Mandarin_duck/Korea/K17-1894/2017	303641 H5N6	Jung Hoon Kwon (Konkuk University / College of Veterinary Medicine)	Konkuk University	Avian diseases laboratory, College of Veterinary Medicine, Konkuk University
A/Mandarin_duck/Korea/K17-1896/2017	303642 H5N6	Jung Hoon Kwon (Konkuk University / College of Veterinary Medicine)	Konkuk University	Avian diseases laboratory, College of Veterinary Medicine, Konkuk University
A/Mandarin_duck/Korea/K18-3/2018	303643 H5N6	Jung Hoon Kwon (Konkuk University / College of Veterinary Medicine)	Konkuk University	Avian diseases laboratory, College of Veterinary Medicine, Konkuk University
A/Domestic_Duck/Netherlands/EMC-2/2018	305416 H5N6	Maria Johanna Poen (Erasmus Medical Center / Department of Virology)	Erasmus Medical Center	Erasmus Medical Center
A/Domestic_Duck/Netherlands/EMC-6/2018	305417 H5N6	Maria Johanna Poen (Erasmus Medical Center / Department of Virology)	Erasmus Medical Center	Erasmus Medical Center
A/Jungle_crow/Hyogo/2803A002/2018	308781 H5N6			
A/Jungle_crow/Hyogo/2803E011/2018	308782 H5N6			
A/Jungle_crow/Hyogo/2803E022/2018	308783 H5N6			
A/duck/Democratic Republic of the Congo/17RS882-29/2017	308802 H5N8			
A/duck/Democratic Republic of the Congo/17RS882-33/2017	308803 H5N8			
A/duck/Democratic Republic of the Congo/17RS882-40/2017	308804 H5N8			
A/duck/Democratic Republic of the Congo/17RS882-5/2017	308805 H5N8			
A/Brahma_chicken/Belgium/6153/2017	309197 H5N8			
A/Guinea_fowl/Belgium/6102/2017	309198 H5N8			
A/Armenian_Gull/Republic of Georgia/4/2017	312376 H5N6	Maria Johanna Poen (Erasmus Medical Center / Department of Virology)	Erasmus Medical Center	National Center for Disease Control and Public Health, Georgia
A/tufted_duck/Shimane/3211TY001/2017	319652 H5N6			
A/chicken/Kursk/284/2018	320607 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Kursk/526/2018	320608 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Samara/446/2018	320657 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Samara/447/2018	320658 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/duck/Samara/452/2018	320659 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/goose/Samara/455/2018	320660 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/goose/Samara/459/2018	320661 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Penza/300/2018	320662 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Penza/301/2018	320663 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Orel/533/2018	320664 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Rostov-on-Don/766/2018	320674 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/turkey/Rostov-on-Don/817/2018	320675 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Penza/605/2018	320676 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Penza/607/2018	320677 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Cheboksary/805/2018	320678 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Cheboksary/806/2018	320679 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Kursk/757/2018	320680 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Kursk/760/2018	320681 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Kursk/762/2018	320682 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/goose/Samara/673/2018	320683 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/goose/Samara/675/2018	320684 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Samara/679/2018	320685 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Cheboksary/849/2018	320953 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Cheboksary/850/2018	320954 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Cheboksary/851/2018	320955 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Cheboksary/853/2018	320956 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Cheboksary/854/2018	320957 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/chicken/Tatarstan/7/2018	320958 H5N8	Ivan Susloparov (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	
A/mute_swan/Netherlands/20015931-001/2020	591075 H5N8	Rene Heutink (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/chicken/Netherlands/20016597-026030/2020	603132 H5N8	Rene Heutink (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eurasian_Wigeon/Netherlands/1/2020	603133 H5N1	Theo Bestebrøer (Erasmus Medical Center / Department of Virology)	Erasmus Medical Center	Erasmus Medical Center
A/Eurasian_Wigeon/Netherlands/4/2020	603134 H5N1	Theo Bestebrøer (Erasmus Medical Center / Department of Virology)	Erasmus Medical Center	Erasmus Medical Center
A/Eurasian_Wigeon/Netherlands/5/2020	603135 H5N1	Theo Bestebrøer (Erasmus Medical Center / Department of Virology)	Erasmus Medical Center	Erasmus Medical Center
A/Eurasian_Wigeon/Netherlands/7/2020	603136 H5N8	Theo Bestebrøer (Erasmus Medical Center / Department of Virology)	Erasmus Medical Center	Erasmus Medical Center
A/mute_swan/Kazakhstan/1-267-20-B/2020	614401 H5N8	Alex Byrne (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) / Virology Department)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	National Veterinary Reference Center
A/domestic_goose/Kazakhstan/1-261_2-20-B/2020	615065 H5N8	Alex Byrne (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) / Virology Department)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	National Veterinary Reference Center
A/domestic_goose/Kazakhstan/1-248_2-20-B/2020	615068 H5N8	Alex Byrne (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) / Virology Department)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	National Veterinary Reference Center
A/domestic_duck/Kazakhstan/1-274-20-B/2020	615072 H5N8	Alex Byrne (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) / Virology Department)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	National Veterinary Reference Center
A/domestic_goose/Kazakhstan/1-242_2-20-B/2020	615073 H5N8	Alex Byrne (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) / Virology Department)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	National Veterinary Reference Center
A/chicken/Iraq/1/2020	623074 H5N8	Alex Byrne (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) / Virology Department)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	Central Veterinary Labs
A/whooper_swan/Inner Mongolia/w1-1/2020	625671 H5N8	Hongliang Chai (Northeast Forestry University / College of Wildlife Resources)	Northeast Forestry University	College of Wildlife and Protected Areas, Northeast Forestry University
A/mute_swan/Inner Mongolia/w2-1/2020	625672 H5N8	Hongliang Chai (Northeast Forestry University / College of Wildlife Resources)	Northeast Forestry University	College of Wildlife and Protected Areas, Northeast Forestry University
A/chicken/Russian_Federation/Omsk/1680-10/2020	626647 H5N5	Alex Byrne (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) / Virology Department)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	Federal Centre for Animal Health (ARRIAH)
A/goose/Russian_Federation/Omsk/1680-6/2020	626648 H5N5	Alex Byrne (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) / Virology Department)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	Federal Centre for Animal Health (ARRIAH)
A/duck/Russian_Federation/Saratov/1578-2/2020	626649 H5N8	Alex Byrne (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) / Virology Department)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	Federal Centre for Animal Health (ARRIAH)
A/duck/Russian_Federation/Omsk/1328-2/2020	626650 H5N8	Alex Byrne (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) / Virology Department)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	Federal Centre for Animal Health (ARRIAH)
A/goose/Russian_Federation/Kurgan/1345-25/2020	626651 H5N8	Alex Byrne (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) / Virology Department)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	Federal Centre for Animal Health (ARRIAH)
A/chicken/England/030720/2020	626652 H5N8	Alex Byrne (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) / Virology Department)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)
A/greylag_goose/Netherlands/20016582-004/2020	632314 H5N1	Rene Heutink (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/Eurasian_teal/Netherlands/20016896-013/2020	632315 H5N1	Rene Heutink (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/barnacle_goose/Netherlands/20016935-002/2020	632317 H5N8	Rene Heutink (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/greylag_goose/Netherlands/20016879-001/2020	632318 H5N8	Rene Heutink (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/duck/Chelyabinsk/1207-1/2020	637098 H5N8	Nikolay Zinyakov (Federal Centre for Animal Health (ARRIAH) / OIE Regional Reference Laboratory)	Federal Centre for Animal Health (ARRIAH)	Federal Centre for Animal Health (ARRIAH) OIE Regional Reference Laboratory
A/chicken/Netherlands/20016978-001/2020	641377 H5N8	Rene Heutink (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/chicken/Netherlands/20017639-001/2020	641394 H5N8	Rene Heutink (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/chicken/Netherlands/20017694-004/2020	641395 H5N8	Rene Heutink (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research)	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
A/turkey/Omsk/0001/2020	644121 H5N8	Natalia Goncharova (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)
A/goose/Omsk/0002/2020	644122 H5N8	Natalia Goncharova (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)
A/turkey/Omsk/0003/2020	644123 H5N8	Natalia Goncharova (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)
A/duck/Omsk/0004/2020	644124 H5N8	Natalia Goncharova (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)
A/goose/Omsk/0111/2020	644125 H5N8	Natalia Goncharova (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)
A/chicken/Omsk/0112/2020	644126 H5N8	Natalia Goncharova (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)
A/goose/Omsk/0113/2020	644127 H5N8	Natalia Goncharova (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)
A/goose/Omsk/0114/2020	644128 H5N8	Natalia Goncharova (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)
A/goose/Omsk/0115/2020	644129 H5N8	Natalia Goncharova (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)
A/goose/Omsk/01161/2020	644130 H5N8	Natalia Goncharova (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)
A/goose/Omsk/01171/2020	644132 H5N8	Natalia Goncharova (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)
A/chicken/Omsk/0118/2020	644134 H5N8	Natalia Goncharova (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)
A/chicken/Omsk/0119/2020	644135 H5N8	Natalia Goncharova (State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR) / Emerging Zoonot	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)	State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology (VECTOR)

